

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Authoring Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarker Tables

Procedures for constructing ASCT+B tables

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Introduction

The procedures outlined in this document describe how Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) tables are authored. The tables are a critical part of the evolving Human Reference Atlas. See Börner et al. 2021 for background information. This SOP is designed for table authors and reviewers who are creating these tables, although it may be of use as a reference for others who wish to understand how these tables are built.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Human Reference Atlas Project Manager (HRA PM)** is responsible for providing ASCT+B table templates and organizational documents to Lead Organ Contacts, facilitating communication between parties, and tracking progress.

The **Lead Organ Contact (LOC)** is a domain expert for the organ of focus. They serve as the lead table author and take responsibility for providing and verifying the contents of an ASCT+B table with all co-authors.

External Reviewers are organ domain experts that have not authored the content of the ASCT+B table.

The **Ontology Validator** is an ontology expert that codes and runs a Python script called CCF_Tools each week. The script reads in ASCT+B Master table sheets, compares them against the RDF triple store database called Ubergraph (Uberon and Cell Ontology), and outputs a validation report that can be used to improve tables.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Project Manager	Nancy Ruschman	ccfinfo@iu.edu
Lead Organ Contact	various	

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External Reviewer	various	
Ontology Validators	James McLaughlin Aleix Puig	jmcl@ebi.ac.uk aleix@ebi.ac.uk

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Procedures

Before beginning the table, gather reference materials

- Read about the goals, data formats, and use of the Human Reference Atlas in Börner et al. 2021 and Osumi-Sutherland et al. 2021.
- Subject matter experts for each organ create or review ASCT+B tables every 6 months according to the schedule in Table 2.
- Each Lead Author then submits the table to the MC-IU team.
- The MC-IU team coordinates external review of the table by organ experts who have not been involved in authoring the table.
- The MC-IU team gathers metadata, perfects formatting of the table and submits the table for additional ontology mapping validation checks.

Tasks	Submission Deadline	HRA Release
Table submission	April 1 and October 1	June 15 and December 15
Revisions that arise during validation	May 1 and November 1	June 15 and December 15

Table 2. Table Submission Deadlines and Human Reference Atlas (HRA) Release Timeline.

- Digital object identifiers (DOIs) are issued as part of each Human Reference Atlas (HRA) release and published on the HRA portal: <https://humanatlas.io/asctb-tables> in June and December. DOIs are requested by the MC-IU team as part of the HRA release process.
- The Lead Author gathers publication and data references that demonstrate relationships between anatomical structures, cell types, and biomarker sets (genes, proteins, proteoforms, lipids, or metabolites) that uniquely identify cell types and the anatomical structures in which those cell types are located. A biomarker set will uniquely characterize the cell type.
- When authoring an ASCT+B table, the Lead Author should include gross anatomical structures that are required to accurately place a tissue block into a 3D reference organ. Include any necessary ducts, veins, arteries or other structures that they would use to facilitate placement of a tissue block within the organ. Please refer to the tissue

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Registration User Interface (RUI) at <https://humanatlas.io/registration-user-interface> and review the video demo <https://youtu.be/18imQj068lw?si=purdWwwZDFXcM-ov>.

- The lead author will familiarize themselves with common ontologies used by the ASCT+B effort:
 - Uber anatomy (Uberon) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/uberontologies/uberontologies>
 - Foundational Models of Anatomy (FMA) <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/FMA>
 - Cell Ontology (CL) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/cellontologies/cellontologies>
- The lead author will familiarize themselves with the ontology repositories that serve those ontologies:
 - The National Center for Biomedical Ontology (NCBO) <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>
 - Ontology Look-up Service (OLS) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies>
- The lead author will familiarize themselves with tools to facilitate finding and filling in gene and protein names and IDs:
 - Human Gene Ontology Gene Nomenclature (HGNC) Multi-symbol checker <https://www.genenames.org/tools/multi-symbol-checker/>.
 - Transform the UniProt Accession Number into HGNC IDs, copy and paste the UniProt accession numbers into the box here: <https://www.uniprot.org/uploadlists/>
- The lead author will review the Visible Human Massively Open Online Course (VHMOOC) modules for “7. Ontologies 101”, and “8. Anatomical Structures, Cell Types, and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables”, which are freely available here: <https://expand.iu.edu/browse/sice/cns/courses/hubmap-visible-human-mooc>
- The Lead Author will need to attend the monthly HRA Working Group meetings. Sign up at https://iu.co1.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_bpaBhlr8XfdiNRH to receive meeting reminders.
- The lead author will familiarize themselves with the resources and tools on the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) <https://humanatlas.io/>, with a focus on existing ASCT+B tables, their metadata pages, and the ASCT+B Reporter tool.
- If the Lead Author and reviewers do not already have an ORCID, they need to sign up for one here: <https://orcid.org>.
- Review the ASCT+B flattened, machine-readable master table format
 - The lead author will be provided with the blank ASCT+B template, found here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1smQ8_3F-KSRIY7bmzsoM1EonQL4ahNaXP7zeQFf3Ko/edit?usp=sharing. Each row of the ASCT+B master table can be thought of as one record in a database.

ASCT+B table metadata

The first 10 rows of the ASCT+B Google sheet template are reserved for the following information:

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Row 1	Organ Name	Provide organ name: “Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers Table for *Organ Name* ”
Row 2	Intentionally left blank	
Row 3	Author names (lead author first; co-authors following; up to 3 primary authors)	First name, middle initial, last name (Example format: Jane M. Doe; John Q. Public; etc.)
Row 4	Author(s) ORCID (same order as author names in row 3)	(semi-colons should be used between ORCIDs) Example format: 0000-0000-0000-0000; 0000-0000-0000-0000; 0000-0000-0000-0000
Row 5	Reviewer Name(s) (up to 6 reviewers)	Format should be reviewer 1 first name, middle initial last name; reviewer 2 first name, middle initial last name etc (Example format: Jackie M. Doe; Jessie Q. Public; etc). Both internal and external reviewers should be included.
Row 6	Reviewer(s) ORCID(s) (same order as reviewer names in row 5)	(semi-colons should be used between ORCIDs) Example format: 0000-0000-0000-0000; 0000-0000-0000-0000; 0000-0000-0000-0000
Row 7	General publication(s)	Please provide links to major papers that provide scientific evidence for the nodes (AS, CT, B) and links (relationships between them) in the part_of AS tree and the AS-CT and CT-B bimodal networks. Semi-colons should be used between DOIs Reference DOIs should use this format: “DOI:10.1016/j.exphem.2018.09.004.”
Row 8	Data DOI	DOI will be added by the HRA Project Manager upon publication to the HRA portal.
Row 9	Date	Date that table is published and available on the HRA portal
Row 10	Version number	Table version number will be added upon publication to the HRA Portal with DOI.

Table 3. ASCT+B table metadata descriptions.

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ASCT+B table integration with the ASCT+B Reporter visualization application

The individual rows in the ASCT+B table can be thought of as equivalent to one record in a database, where each column represents a field in the record.

Row 11	Column headers	These are used by the companion ASCT+B Reporter visualization tool and MUST conform to the format provided.
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Row 11 column headers are used by the companion ASCT+B Reporter visualization tool

- The column headers are parsed and used by the ASCT+B Reporter to compute a visualization of the data. All headers must conform to the format given below or they will not appear in the ASCT+B Reporter visualizations.
- What do the column headers (fields) mean?
 - For each anatomical structure (AS), cell type (CT) or biomarker (B) there are 3 required columns and several optional columns that may be added as needed.
- ENTITY values:

AS	Anatomical structures. AS/1 is the organ name, other AS should have the relationship of part to whole (<i>part_of</i>) in the ontology used with the previous AS in a row.
CT	Cell Types that are part of the last anatomical structure in the row.
BProtein	Protein biomarker; this data comes from many types of assays. Flow cytometry, multiplexed immunofluorescence imaging, spatial proteomics, etc
BGene	Gene biomarker; this data is typically referring to differentially expressed genes
BProteoform	Proteoform biomarker; this data is from proteoform imaging mass spectrometry like nanospray desorption electrospray ionization (nanoDESI)
BLipid	Lipid biomarkers; this data is from imaging mass spectrometry.
BMetabolite	Metabolite biomarkers; this data is from imaging mass spectrometry.
REF	(required) References that support the AS-AS, AS-CT, CT-B relationships provided in the table. Provide reference DOIs using this format: "DOI: 10.1016/j.exphem.2018.09.004."

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NUMBER	(required) can be non-negative numbers starting from 1
NUMBER DATA_TYPE values	ID, LABEL, DOI (optional)

Table 4. ASCT+B table metadata descriptions used by the ASCT+B Table Reporter.

- To add additional columns per entity type
 - If you need to ADD several levels of depth of Anatomical structures (AS) to the table, add 3 columns per AS and change the number.
 - Examples: AS/1, AS/1/LABEL, AS/1/ID, AS/2, AS/2/LABEL, AS/2/ID etc.
 - n: represents number in examples below
 - AS/n: name given the anatomical structure by the subject matter expert (SME)
 - Example: AS/3 Moderator band
 - AS/n/LABEL: the Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS) “rdfs:label” name given the anatomical structure in the ontology (this may not be exactly the same as that given by the SME.)
 - Example: AS/3/label Septomarginal trabecula
 - Example: AS/n/ID: the unique ID given the anatomical structure in the ontology
 - Example: AS/3/ID FMA:7272
 - The next AS columns would be “AS/4 AS/4/LABEL AS/4/ID” etc.

Determine how to organize the ASCT+B table

- Start by thinking about how to represent the overall three-dimensional structure of the organ as a flattened data table. This can be challenging since there might be multiple ways of doing this.
- Review ways that other ASCT+B tables are organized for ideas (see Figure 1) and try to be as consistent as possible throughout the table.
 - **Lobular.** These organs have repeating nested units. Table Authors have used different starting points. For example, pancreas lists gross anatomical structures, lung starts with one lobe, and liver starts at the lobule level.
 - **Layers.** Examples of organs represented as a set of layers include skin and ureter.
 - **Segments←Layers.** Some layered organs can be divided into segments. However, in general, table authors have chosen to start by listing the segments and then within each segment listing its layers. Examples include fallopian tube, large intestine, ovary, small intestine, spinal cord, urinary bladder, and uterus.
 - **Branching.** The blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and peripheral nervous system tables list structures that branch from other structures.

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- **Tissues←Cells.** Some organs focus on a list of tissues and their cell types and lack a higher level anatomical structure. These include blood, bone marrow, and knee.
- **Collection.** These tables contain collections of structures organized by body region (skeleton and muscular system) or system (anatomical systems).
- **List←Tissues.** In general, these tables contain a list of top level structures (e.g., capsule, follicle, tubules, and vessels) and the tissues in each one. However, some of those top level structures might also have some sub-structures before reaching the tissue level. These organs include Allen brain, eye, heart, kidney, lymph node, main bronchus, palatine tonsil, placenta, prostate, spleen, thymus, trachea.

Figure 1. Examples of how to represent an organ in an ASCT+B table

Add content to flattened ASCT+B master tables

Anatomical structures

- Add anatomical structures (AS) starting with the organ name (i.e., heart, lung, kidney ...) as AS/1
- Please do not use abbreviations for the primary name of the AS, CT or B. Instead, write it out in long form.
 - Example: Instead of writing the abbreviation LV (heart), write out left ventricle
- If abbreviations are common for these terms, please add a column titled AS/1/ABBR substituting the number to match the AS number it is associated with:
 - Example: AS/1/ABBR

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- Example from Heart ASCT+B table for Anatomical structure abbreviation:
AS/2: left ventricle, AS/2/ABBR: LV
- Example from Kidney ASCT+B table for cell type abbreviation:
CT/1: Parietal epithelial cell, CT/1/ABBR: PEC
- Example: (the arrows indicate the structure is part_of the higher order AS)
nephron is part_of kidney. This is the language used to describe in ontological terms as well as anatomically.
 - kidney ← nephron ← renal corpuscle ← Bowman's (glomerular) capsule ← parietal epithelium
- Blood Vasculature, Lymph Vasculature and Peripheral Nervous System (PNS) are treated differently from other anatomical structures because these are "branching part of" structures (large diameter blood vessels often branch and taper in diameter) rather than simple "part of" structures.
 - If you include any of these structures, please provide named structures, rather than general terms, and place them in their appropriate location in the anatomical structure hierarchy. For example, indicate that "kidney arcuate artery UBERON:0001552" is part_of "cortex of kidney UBERON:0001225"
 - Avoid using general terms like "blood vasculature UBERON:0004537". If you do so, please be as specific as possible and at least limit it to your organ (e.g., "kidney vasculature UBERON:0006544").
 - Vessels should not be their own top-level branch of an ASCT+B table (e.g. AS/1).
 - Any vessels in ASCT+B tables should include the cell type "blood vessel endothelial cell" (CL:0000071) so they can be easily found and distinguished from non-vascular structures. Other cell types may be added to vessels.
- For tissue resident immune cells found in non-lymphoid organs (ex. Lymph node, thymus, bone marrow, blood), please use the cell ontology IDs for the particular immune cell.
- Consider adding cell types and biomarkers from other efforts within HuBMAP such as the Organ Mapping Antibody Panels (OMAPs) for multiplexed antibody based imaging techniques and from single cell RNA sequencing. You are encouraged to use reference maps like those produced in Azimuth <https://azimuth.hubmapconsortium.org/>.

Cell types

- Add cell types (CT); there may be more than one CT in a hierarchy similar to how the AS can be nested.
 - Because this is a flattened data table for machine readability, if an AS has four (4) cell types, then repeat all of the higher level structures up to the cell type column four times. The origin of cell types should be based on datasets with supporting literature that is provided in the REF columns.
 - Example: Last AS column thick ascending limb of loop of Henle has four (4) cell types (CT) columns for four rows

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AS/4	CT/1
thick ascending limb of loop of Henle	Thick Ascending Limb Cell (general)
thick ascending limb of loop of Henle	Cortex-TAL cell
thick ascending limb of loop of Henle	Medulla-TAL cell
thick ascending limb of loop of Henle	Macula Densa cell

Table 5. An example of how to document multiple cell types in one anatomical structure.

Biomarker sets

- Add unique biomarkers (B) that characterize the CT for that AS within the organ. A biomarker set will uniquely characterize the cell type. This does NOT mean unique in relation to the whole body, just unique for the organ that the ASCT+B master table covers. The origin of the biomarker set that uniquely defines a cell type within a particular organ should be based on datasets or supporting literature.
 - Biomarkers come in many different forms. The most common are single cell transcriptomics (gene), and proteins (CODEX, FACS/Flow cytometry, proteomics (mass spectrometry)). The ASCT+B reporter supports gene, protein, proteoforms, lipids and metabolite biomarkers.
 - For differentially expressed gene markers, use column headers: BGene/1, BGene/1/LABEL, BGene/1/ID
 - For protein markers, use column headers: BProtein/1 BProtein/1/LABEL BProtein/1/ID
 - For lipid markers, use column headers: BLipid/1, BLipid/1/LABEL, BLipid/1/ID
 - For the BLipid ID column, please use the format LM: plus the LM_ID from the LIPID MAPS database. (Example: SSEA-3 antigen LM_ID LMSP0502AE00 → fill in the BLipid/1/ID column like this: LM:LMSP0502AE00)
 - For metabolite markers, use column headers: BMetabolite/1, BMetabolite/1/LABEL, BMetabolite/1/ID
 - For proteoforms of proteins, use headers: BProteoform/1, BProteoform/1/LABEL, BProteoform/1/ID
 - BProteoform/1: the name the subject matter expert provides
 - BProteoform/1/LABEL: UniProt approved protein name of the canonical protein that the proteoform is a member of.
 - BProteoform/1/ID: the UniProt accession number that matches the UniProt approved protein name.

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Functional tissue units (FTUs)

- Identify at least one major functional tissue unit (FTU) per organ. Functional tissue units (FTUs), such as glomerulus in kidney or crypt in colon, are subregions of tissue that serve a specific function; they are important for bridging the organ-level to single cell level.
 - Add 3 columns as before FTU/1 , FTU/1/LABEL , FTU/1/ID.
 - To the “FTU/1” column, name the FTU that the AS-CT combination is found within, FTU/1/LABEL is the Uberon ontology rdfs:label and FTU/1/ID is the Uberon ID.
 - Functional tissue units (FTUs) for an organ are defined as a three-dimensional block of cells centered around a capillary where each cell is within diffusion distance from any other cell within the same block (de Bono et al. 2013). FTUs perform important physiological functions that are replicated many times within a whole organ (Hayman, Martin, and Miller 1939). The ASCT+B Master tables identify them and the typology of cells and biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, proteoforms, lipid or metabolic markers).
- Provide a list of major publications (REFs) that support the AS-AS, AS-CT, CT-B relationships captured in the ASCT+B master table. Different types of publications can have different types of persistent identifiers.
 - Most journal articles use DOI or PubMed Identifier (PMID) or PMCID; When both are present, preferentially use the digital object identifier (DOI). Use these column headers:
 - Column headings: REF/1, REF/1/DOI, REF/1/NOTES. Add additional columns as required following the the REF/#, REF/#/DOI, REF/#/NOTES column header format.
 - REF/1: provide the bibliographic reference Authors (Year) Title. Venue.
 - REF/1/DOI: unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for the journal article.
 - REF/1/NOTES: Indicate what evidence within the ASCT+B table the reference provides scientific evidence to support (i.e., the part_of AS tree and linkages to CTs but also the CT-B bimodal networks). Example citation for lung: Tables S1 and S2 in <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-020-2922-4> for CT-B and AS-CT associations.
 - For PMCID: substitute REF/1/PMCID for column header: unique links to full-text papers in PubMed Central
 - For PMID: substitute REF/1/PMID for column header: unique links to abstracts in PubMed.
 - For books, use the International Standard Book Number (ISBN), a 13-digit number, used as the unique identifier. Provide reference ISBN using this format:
 - “ISBN 13: 978-0-12-505263-4.”

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- Example : Ref/1 = reference in any format, Ref/1/ISBN and I have a Ref/1/NOTES for information authors want to convey about the ref like AS-CT relationship.
- Column headings: REF/1, Ref/1/ISBN, REF/1/NOTES. Add additional columns as required following the the REF/#, REF/#/ISBN, REF/#/NOTES column header format.
- **REF/1:** provide the bibliographic reference Authors (Year) Title. Venue.
- **REF/1/ISBN:** International Standard Book Number (ISBN), a 13-digit number used to uniquely identify books
- **REF/1/NOTES:** Indicate what evidence within the ASCT+B table the reference provides scientific evidence to support (i.e., the part_of AS tree and linkages to CTs but also the CT-B bimodal networks).
- For websites, use the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) as the unique identifier
 - Column headings: REF/1, REF/1/DOI, REF/1/NOTES. Add additional columns as required following the the REF/#, REF/#/DOI, REF/#/NOTES column header format.
 - REF/1: provide the bibliographic reference Authors (Year) Title. Venue.
 - REF/1/URL: Uniform Resource Locator (URL) is used as the unique identifier of websites.
 - REF/1/NOTES: Indicate what evidence within the ASCT+B table the reference provides scientific evidence to support (i.e., the part_of AS tree and linkages to CTs but also the CT-B bimodal networks). Example citation for lung: Tables S1 and S2 in <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-020-2922-4> for CT-B and AS-CT associations.

Visualize the ASCT+B Table to check relationships between AS-CT and CT-B

ASCT+B Reporter Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ):

<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-asct-reporter/docs/faq>

ASCT+B Reporter Documentation:

<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-asct-reporter/docs/introduction>

To access the playground feature of ASCT+B reporter visualization tool:

- Go to the ASCT+B reporter: <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-asct-reporter/>
- In a separate browser window or tab, go to the ASCT+B table google sheet or spreadsheet formatted with the same template as the ASCT+B Master google sheet table.
- Be certain that the ASCT+B table sharing setting is anyone with the link and copy and paste the browser url address for the table.

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- In the ASCT+B reporter, click go to visualization and click any of the organs (for using the playground, it doesn't matter which one)
- Click on "playground" button (looks like a pencil) at top
- In the playground click on upload and then copy and paste the browser navigation bar url into the space provided. Do not use the copy link from the google sheet share button--this will produce an error.
- Click the Link button, it will then produce a visualization of the table you linked.
- On the left side panel of the ASCT+B reporter, you can manipulate the height or width of the visualization as well as x and y of the nodes.
- There are features to turn on or off ontology IDs, select a particular type of biomarker, look for all terms with missing ontology IDs (will highlight with a box) etc.
- Click on the terminal anatomical structure node to highlight the connections to cell types and biomarkers.
- Similarly, click on the cell type node to highlight terminal AS and all biomarkers associated with CT.

Add ontology term labels and unique identifiers (IDs)

Anatomy, cellular and biomolecular ontologies provide these formalized relationships with unique numerical identifiers that can be mapped to the 3D reference models. Currently, no single ontology exists that captures the complete human body to this resolution; however, several ontologies do exist at different levels of resolution to provide a foundation for this work. Existing ontologies (Uber-anatomy ontology (Uberon)(Mungall et al. 2012)), Foundational Model of Anatomy (FMA) (Rosse and Mejino 2003; Detwiler, Mejino, and Brinkley 2016; Golbreich, Grosjean, and Darmoni 2013), Cell Ontology (CL)(Bard, Rhee, and Ashburner 2005; Bernstein et al. 2021), Human Gene Ontology Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC)(Gray et al. 2016), etc.) have thousands of terms and form a complex knowledge graph. They were designed for different purposes and frequently cover developmental and disease terms.

- Uberon, Foundational Model of Anatomy (FMA), Cell Ontology (CL) and Human Gene Ontology Nomenclature Committee (HGNC) are the main ontologies used to match terms from ASCT+B tables.
- For lipids, LipidMAPS unique identifiers (LM-ID) are described here: https://www.lipidmaps.org/data/classification/lipid_cns.html

Explore ontology using an ontology editor like Protégé

- Browse these ontologies via the links provided directly from a web browser or download the latest version of the ontologies as an .owl file from
 - National Center for Biomedical Ontology (NCBO) Bioportal <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>
 - Uber anatomy <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/UBERON>
 - Foundational Model of Anatomy <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/FMA>
 - Cell Ontology <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/CL>
- To search, browse, and explore them use an ontology editor like Protégé.

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- The Elk reasoner and DL Query were used in the Protégé ontology editor to compile the part_of and located_in relationships found in Uberon and the Cell Ontology between anatomical structures, cell types, and organs in a Google sheet. An example from the first set of eleven organs can be found at https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1cg_HNwANIJq9T9DJa6--PEINftVChQEJ/edit#gid=1869053397.
- An example of the nested anatomical structures for part_of and located_in relationships found in Uberon and the Cell Ontology between anatomical structures, cell types and organs using the Elk reasoner and DL Query output for other organs can be found at <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1b-37AbjPhRtgt5UiblCq9VGDjVhfuJTr>.

Explore ontologies using SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language

- To find cells by location, use this pre-made SPARQL query <http://grlc.io/api/hubmapconsortium/ccf-grlc/ubergraph/> (see image)
- Press GET to open up the dialog

The screenshot shows a web interface for a SPARQL query. At the top left, there is a dropdown menu labeled 'default'. Below it, there is a blue button labeled 'GET' and a text input field containing the query '/cell_by_location Find cells by location'.

- In the parameters section, press Try it out

The screenshot shows a 'Parameters' dialog box. On the right side of the dialog, there is a button labeled 'Try it out'.

- This opens a dialog box (see image) where you can delete the default value of kidney http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0002113 from the location area and paste in the with the anatomical location ID from Uberon that interests you.

The screenshot shows a 'Parameters' dialog box with a 'Cancel' button in the top right corner. It contains a table with two rows of parameters:

Name	Description
location <small>required</small> string(\$iri) (query)	A value of type string (iri) that will substitute ?_location_iri in the original query <input type="text" value="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0002"/>
endpoint string (query)	Alternative endpoint for SPARQL query <input type="text" value="https://ubergraph.apps.renci.org/sparql"/>

At the bottom of the dialog, there is a large blue button labeled 'Execute'.

- To find an anatomical location ID in Uberon, go to the Ontology Look-up service (OLS) and copy and paste the value from the top of the page. Example: Eye http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0000970 into location space.

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- To obtain a list of Human Gene Ontology Gene Nomenclature (HGNC) IDs for genes or proteins, use the Human Gene Ontology Gene Nomenclature (HGNC) Multi-symbol checker <https://www.genenames.org/tools/multi-symbol-checker/>. To transform the UniProt Accession Number into HGNC IDs, copy and paste the UniProt accession numbers into the box here: <https://www.uniprot.org/uploadlists/>. Both allow users to input a list of gene or protein names and accession numbers to obtain a downloadable .csv spreadsheet list of the markers of interest.
- A sample spreadsheet containing a custom download from the HGNC can be found here: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-oy-hNvaDc4uhYWWdM_NUSmHbvAE2pG/view. It provides:
 - HGNC ID, Approved symbol, Approved name, Status, Previous symbols, Alias symbols, Chromosome, Accession numbers, RefSeq IDs, UniProt ID (supplied by UniProt), Ensembl ID (supplied by Ensembl), RefSeq (supplied by NCBI), NCBI Gene ID (supplied by NCBI), and Pubmed IDs for supporting reference literature.
- For those entities without any Uberon, FMA, or CL ontology match, fill only the columns for AS/n, CT/n, where n is the appropriate number in the hierarchy of AS or CT.
- Leave blank columns with headers: AS/n/LABEL or CT/n/LABEL (these are names found in ontologies, specifically the Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS) label “rdfs:label”).
- Leave blank columns with headers: AS/n/ID or CT/#/ID (these are the ontology IDs usually in format Uberon:nnnn, CL:nnnn or FMAAnnnn where n=number).
- Proteoforms: <https://www.topdownproteomics.org/>
- Lipids: LipidOntology (LION) (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/LION>) derived from LipidMAPS. Please use the format LM: plus the LM_ID from the LIPID MAPS database. (Example: SSEA-3 antigen LM_ID LMSP0502AE00 → fill in the BLipid/1/ID column with this: LM:LMSP0502AE00)
- Metabolites: Human Metabolome Database <https://hmdb.ca/> and Metlin 2 <https://metlincloud2.massconsortium.com/auth-login.html>

Requesting anatomical structure or cell type additions to Uberon or Cell Ontologies

ASCT+B table authors may find the need for additional anatomical nomenclature, cell types, relationships between those entities or synonyms need to be added. This can be accomplished using either of these two methods:

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- If you would like the Lead Organ Contact to facilitate the New Term Request, please fill in the appropriate organ tab or (create a copy of the template) for New Term requests here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BihrOU9vWrsA_wYjcbdPUr42_Sb22CO3gkBDieiYQPs/edit?usp=sharing
- Alternatively, authors may wish to directly interact with Uberon or Cell Ontology (CL) curators by initiating a new issue using the provided templates in the respective GitHub repository for Uberon <https://github.com/obophenotype/uberont/issues> or Cell Ontology <https://github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology/issues>

Checklist for ASCT+B Table Finalization

Lead authors should use the following checklist at the end of the review process to make sure the new table is complete and ready for external review and publication.

1. Carefully review metadata rows #1-10 of your table. The HRA Project Manager will add version numbers, DOIs and publication dates to the table.
2. Check your AS, CT, B against <http://biocc.hrbmu.edu.cn/CellMarker> which lists data and publication evidence.
3. Compare your vasculature terms with the data Griffin Weber shared. See Blood_Vasculature_v1.3_EXTENDED Vasculature table (revised October 25, 2022) https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11tkcqqz-cpUrfhUQvt5cSn2ntvOrv47ZoZte_D-MS8U/edit#gid=260079318
4. Unify References--whenever possible, provide DOIs using this format: "DOI: 10.1016/j.exphem.2018.09.004."
5. Use NOTES field to indicate if the reference refers to the existence of an entity (e.g., CT) or relationship (e.g., CT-B). Flag any references to non-human datasets with a [NonHum] in NOTES field.
6. Ask other authors to do one final review. Make sure to add all of their names in row #5 in your ASCT+B table. Provide correct full name, affiliation. Add ORCIDs for reviewers in Row #6 so we can acknowledge them properly.
7. Identify other independent experts that can review and approve the table for publication during the external review phase.
8. Let the HRA Project Manager know the table is ready for a compliance check. MC-IU will then confirm that the table meets ASCT+B Reporter requirements--including containing an accurate list of ORCIDs for all authors and reviewers that contributed to table construction.

Validation and Review Process

- The Lead Organ Contact invites additional experts to review and verify AS-AS, AS-CT, CT-B relationships and ontology term choices and definitions. Working with multiple experts in the field leads to greater consensus and higher adoption rates for nomenclature and relationships.
- Authors may reach out to MC-IU for assistance via infoccf@iu.edu.

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- MC-IU validation of AS-AS, AS-CT relationships against Uberon and Cell Ontology will occur weekly using the validation pipeline described in detail here: https://github.com/obophenotype/asct-b_validation, authored by David Osumi-Sutherland and Anita Caron using CCF Tools <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-validation-tools>.

Figure 2. From ASCT+B table to validated OWL

- MC-IU then sends completed ASCT+B tables out for external review and shares feedback with lead authors.
- Lead authors edit tables as needed to incorporate reviewer suggestions and inconsistencies identified during ontology validations.
- Lead authors must update the header to reflect updates. Visualizing the relationships in the ASCT+B master tables using the [ASCT+B Reporter](#) may be useful at this stage.
- Authors inform MC-IU via email at infoccf@iu.edu of updates and problems.

ASCT+B publishing

Publishing ASCT+B Master tables takes several forms.

- ASCT+B master tables that have been validated for *part_of* relationships, internally reviewed and approved by the Lead Organ Contact are uploaded to the CCF Releases GitHub repository <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases>.
- Starting in Y4 of HuBMAP, MASTER tables will be published as part of CCF.OWL ontology on BioPortal <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/CCF>
- The original eleven master tables for kidney, spleen, thymus, lymph node, lung, large intestine, skin, brain, blood & bone marrow, heart and vasculature were published in Börner et al. 2021.
- ASCT+B table information will also be used to incorporate new terms and relationships into existing ontologies (e.g., Uberon and Cell Ontology) as appropriate.

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Glossary

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D spatial objects (e.g., anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials, and surface color and texture. They are created by medical illustrators with the involvement of subject matter experts following standard operating procedures.

Anatomical structure (AS): A distinct biological entity with a 3D volume and shape, e.g., an organ, functional tissue unit (FTU), or cell.

ASCT+B MASTER table: The first ASCT+B table for an organ system to which other ASCT+B-like information may be compared, using the ASCT+B Reporter compare feature.

ASCT+B Reporter: The ASCT+B Reporter is a visualization tool for displaying anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers (ASCT+B) tables for different human organs developed by domain experts. The tables are used to develop a common coordinate framework (CCF) of the healthy human body, <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-asct-reporter>.

ASCT+B Tables: ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types, and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid, or metabolic markers). Cellular identity is supported by scientific evidence and linked to ontologies.

Bimodal network: A network involving two node types and the relationships between them.

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Biomarkers: Molecular, histological, morphological, radiological, physiological or anatomical features that help to characterize the biological state of the body. Here we focus on the molecular markers that can be measured to characterize a cell type. They include genes (BG), proteins (BP), metabolites (BM), proteoforms (BF), and lipids (BL).

Cell types: Mammalian cells are biological units with a defined function that typically have a nucleus and cytoplasm surrounded by a membrane. Each cell type may have broad common functions across organs and specialized functions or morphological or molecular features within each organ or region. Tissue is composed of different (resident and transitory) cell types that are characterized or identified via biomarkers.

CO-Detection by indEXing (CODEX): Multiparameter imaging method that relies on oligonucleotide-conjugated antibodies and the cyclic addition and removal of complementary fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide probes. The commercial fluidics and high-plex image acquisition platform (Akoya Biosciences, Marlborough, MA) for this method enables whole slide imaging of up to 100 biomarkers on tissue samples in situ (Black et al. 2021; Goltsev et al. 2018; Kennedy-Darling et al. 2021).

Common Coordinate Framework (CCF): As used in the Human Reference Atlas, this consists of ontologies and reference object libraries, computer software (e.g., user interfaces) and training materials that (1) enable biomedical experts to semantically annotate tissue samples and to precisely describe their locations in the human body (“registration”), (2) align multi-modal tissue data extracted from different individuals to a reference coordinate system (“mapping”), and to (3) provide tools for searching and browsing HuBMAP data at multiple levels from the whole body down to single cells (“exploration”). See also <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf/>

Crosswalk: An ontological mapping of terms in the Human Reference Atlas digital objects (e.g., 2/3D reference objects, OMAPs, Azimuth references) to ontology terms in the ASCT+B tables.

Digital Object Identifier (DOI): Centrally registered identifier composed of a string of numbers, letters and symbols used to uniquely identify an article or document with a permanent web address or Uniform Resource Locator (URL).

Exploration User Interface (EUI): An interface developed by MC-IU to explore tissue, see <https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>.

FACS: Fluorescence-activated cell sorting uses fluorescently tagged antibodies to cell surface markers most commonly to sort populations of cells into different containers based on markers present.

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FBX (Filmbox) file format: A proprietary file format (.fbx) developed by Kaydara and owned by Autodesk since 2006. It is used to provide interoperability between digital content creation applications.

Flattened data table: A database that stores data in a plain text file where each row of the spreadsheet file holds one record, with fields separated in columns.

Flow cytometry: Similar to FACS without sorting cells into containers, visually represents cell populations based on fluorescent marker presence or absence.

Functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization, i.e. a set of cells, that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ. FTUs can be hierarchically nested.

GitHub: An online service for version control and code-sharing.

GLB file format: Also called GL Transmission Format Binary file (.glb), this is a 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb>.

Healthy tissue: Pathologically unremarkable tissue that can be used to derive the function of healthy cells. What counts as healthy is influenced by normal aging, underlying comorbidities and medical interventions before tissue donation.

International Standard Book Number (ISBN): A 13-digit number that is used as a unique identifier for a specific book, a book edition, or any other book-like products. An ISBN number can be used to identify the book's code digits, language, publisher, book title, edition, and format.

Lipid: Lipids are molecules that contain hydrocarbons and make up the building blocks of the structure and function of living cells. Examples of lipids include fats, oils, waxes, certain vitamins (such as A, D, E and K), hormones and most of the cell membrane that is not made up of protein.

Metabolite: A substance made or used when the body breaks down food, drugs or chemicals, or its own tissue (for example, fat or muscle tissue).

OBJ file format: 3D file format specification, see <https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~mbz/personal/graphics/obj.html>

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Ontology: A set of subject area concepts (here, anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers), their properties and the relationships between them. Ontologies used in the Human Reference Atlas include Uberon and Cell Ontology (CL).

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID): Unique identifier number researchers own and control that connects the iD with professional information — affiliations, grants, publications, etc. and can be used during the publication process. See <https://orcid.org>.

Partonomy: A classification hierarchy that represents part–whole relationships.

Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURL): A uniform resource locator (URL) (i.e., location-based uniform resource identifier or URI) that is used to redirect to the location of the requested web resource. PURLs redirect HTTP clients using HTTP status codes.

Principal Investigator (PI): Person who is responsible for the overall conduct of the research at a given site.

Protégé: An ontology editor, see <https://protege.stanford.edu>.

Proteoform: all of the different molecular forms of a protein product from a single gene that can be found, including changes due to genetic variations, alternatively spliced RNA transcripts and post-translational modifications.

PubMed Central reference number (PMCID): This unique identifier links to full-text papers in PubMed Central, a free full-text archive of biomedical and life sciences journal literature at the U.S. National Institutes of Health's National Library of Medicine (NIH/NLM).

PubMed reference number (PMID) links to abstracts in PubMed, which comprises more than 34 million citations for biomedical literature from MEDLINE, life science journals, and online books.

Rdfs:label: [Resource Description Framework Schema \(RDFS\)](#) label is a human-readable version of a resource's name and is a standard for data interchange, developed and agreed upon by World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and used for the preferred name in an ontology.

Registration User Interface (RUI): Registration user interface developed by MC-IU, available via HuBMAP Data Ingest Portal and at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/rui>.

ROBOT: an ontology tool for automating ontology workflows, see <http://robot.obolibrary.org>.

Role: One's position on a team.

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Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g. plain English).

Task: A piece of work, usually undertaken as part of a larger project.

Typology: A classification that represents general types (e.g. cell types and biomarker types).

Uniform Resource Locator (URL): Identifies the web address or location of a unique resource; however, its authority consists of a domain name and port.

Visible Human (VH): The Visible Human Male and Visible Human datasets are provided by the National Library of Medicine (NLM)(Ackerman 2016).

Web Ontology Language (.OWL) file format: The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) Web Ontology Language is a Semantic Web language documented at <https://www.w3.org/OWL>.

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